

**THE IMAGE AND SIMILAR FATE OF BLACK WOMEN IN THEIR
EYES WERE WATCHING GOD BY NORA ZEALE HURSTON****Abdirakhmonova Gulnora**

Literature faculty of Uzbekistan state of world languages university

Annotation: Their Eyes Were Watching God is a 1937 novel by American author Zora Neale Hurston. It is taken into consideration a traditional of the Harlem Renaissance and Hurston's excellent regarded work. The novel tells the story of Janie Crawford's the path of fate similar to her generation and personal developmental life across three marriages .

Key words: Image , the same events of generation , mental and social problems, burden of the life , hope to be an independent.

Zora Neale Hurston was an American author and filmmaker. She has published her researches which portray the race struggles in the American South in the early 20th century. In her early career

She also wrote fiction about contemporary issues in the black community and became a central figure in her Harlem renaissance. . She is the author of many books, including Jonah's Gourd Vine; Mules and Men; Seraph on the Suwanee; Moses, Man of the Mountain; Every Tongue Got to Confess; and Their Eyes Were Watching God. Her most popular of her four novels is Their Eyes Were Watching God, published in 1937. Hurston's life began in Eatonville, where their eyes were on God. Founded in 1866, this tiny, pitch-black city is on the road between Florida Highway 17 and Interstate 4, It is located approximately 8 km north of Orlando . Hurston never left the small town of Eatonville, neither in his professional career as an anthropologist and writer, nor in his personal life. She later used Eatonville as the setting for many of her stories.

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¹ Page 256(about the author)

“A deeply soulful novel that comprehends love and cruelty, and separates the big people from the small of heart, without ever losing sympathy for those unfortunates who don’t know how to live properly.” —Zadie Smith.

From the point of above , Absolutely Many of black women live at the bottom of society; they were subjected to both sexual oppression and racism. In *Their Eyes were watching God*, writer Zora Neale Hurston creates a positive image of Janie pursuing women's rights and self-fulfillment. In Janie's pilgrimage for women's rights, she goes through three stages, Janie's loss, Janie's awakening, and Janie's blossoming. Janie's struggle embodies black feminist awareness, becoming an independent woman and having a prominent voice in a male-dominated world.

This study analyzes attitudes toward black women in their family roles of grandmother, mother, mate and daughter as portrayed in Harlem Renaissance literature. This period lasted from about 1924 to 1934. A study of her work sheds light on the intellectual, social and literary history of black people over the 75 years in which they collectively describe and appraise the lives of black women from slavery to the Depression years. The work discusses Nora Zeal Hurston's attitude towards intellectual and social interests directly related to Negro women. It is love story about a woman who isn't afraid to defy convention *Life and Love* . Quoted by the grandmother in the same work .

One of the most influential figures in Renaissance literature

Hurston has often been criticized for her reluctance in the novel.

In their publications, she criticizes and even points out fractional injustice. For the most part it drew on lower class blacks and their folklore focus of her work.

“When Janie had finished indoors she sat down in the barn with the potatoes. But springtime reached her in there so she moved everything to a place in the yard where she could see the road. The noon sun

filtered through the leaves of the fine oak tree where she sat and made lacy patterns on the ground. She had been there a long time when she heard whistling coming down the road”

Across the country, a black woman became a surrogate a white woman who takes care of her children, takes care of her household, prepares food for their family and also non-traditional women's duties and

The black woman also faced other mental and social problems .

The fact that lower paying jobs and family commitments

shunned by the rest of society became her lot. Family breakdowns and migration tendencies often forced the black woman to struggle with life saving difficulties. Black women traditionally earned less than everyone else and burden of loads of housework .

The writer has very beautifully interpreted the life of the female negroes in their family status . Especially we can see this in the image of Jane's grandmother, the nanny. At that time, the fate of black women was in a very sad state, and even these conditions were passed down from generation to generation. As in the case of his daughters even in his grandchildren. From the novel we realized that not only nanny but also her daughter Leafy had the same bad and unpleased fate , Nanny did not want her daughter to experience the terrible incident that happened to her,

she wanted her daughter to be educated and marry a good man, but unfortunately, at the age of 17, her daughter was abused by her white teacher just like her mother. After being pregnant by white man. She gave birth to her daughter Jane, she left her family and chose another ways.

“Yeah, Janie, youse got yo’ womanhood on yuh. So Ah mout ez well tell yuh whut Ah been savin’ up for uh spell. Ah wants to see you married right away.”^{45/260}

“Me, married? Naw, Nanny, no ma’am! Whut Ah know ’bout uh

husband?”

“Whut Ah seen just now is plenty for me, honey, Ah don’t want no trashy nigger, no breath-and-britches, lak Johnny Taylor usin’ yo’ body to wipe his foots on.”

After that, Nanny didn't like this situation for her granddaughter and take her up. However, because of society's attitude towards black women, Jane's behavior changed, she was forced to marry by her nanny to an old rich black man in order to live full of herself so that she wouldn't be like her mother.

“Janie and Logan got married in Nanny’s parlor of a Saturday evening with three cakes and big platters of fried rabbit and chicken. Everything to eat in abundance.”

Jane was not happy in her marriage because she was a happy romantic girl in life and there she was forced to do housework like all black women. Then she decided to escape and began her life with new pages. She fell in love with the man who was also rich and handsome, But he was jealous of Jane and forced her to wear long blue clothes and wore her hair like a bun that all the time. But that was not Jane’s wish, she wanted to be independent woman and last reached it. Their Eyes Were Watching God concludes with Janie’s self-actualization and hope for her own future.

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